

HISTORY OF THE WORLD TRADE ORGANIZATION (WTO)

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The World Trade Organization (WTO) occupies a central place in the international trading system, regulating and streamlining global trade relations. Founded in 1995, the WTO is the successor to the General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade (GATT), which began its work in 1948. The history of the WTO is a complex path associated with the development of international trade and economic relations at the global level. In this article, we will consider the key stages of the formation and development of the WTO, based on Russian sources and research.

International trade has a long history, starting with ancient trade routes such as the Silk Road that connected East and West. These early forms of trade were often regulated by local rules and agreements, but global trade trends began to take shape in Modern times. With the rise of colonial empires and the Industrial Revolution, trade barriers began to disappear, and the need for more orderly and universal trade rules became apparent.¹

The idea of creating an international trade organization dates back to the end of World War II, when the international community realized the need for a new order in international trade. At the Bretton Woods Conference in 1944, along with the creation of the International Monetary Fund (IMF) and the World Bank, the creation of the International Trade Organization (ITO) was discussed. However, despite the efforts, the creation of the ITO proved impossible due to political differences and changes in the international political environment.²

Instead, the General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade (GATT) was signed in 1947, which entered into force in 1948. The GATT began as a temporary agreement, but over time it became the basis for regulating international trade. According to G.V. Maksakova, the GATT proved successful in reducing tariffs and trade barriers, which contributed to the rapid growth of international trade in the post-war period.

The evolution of the GATT and the rounds of negotiations:

GATT has conducted a series of rounds of negotiations aimed at further reducing trade barriers and tariffs. The most important of these rounds include:

¹ Pomeranz, Kenneth. "The Great Divergence: China, Europe, and the Making of the Modern World Economy". Princeton University Press, 2000.

² Федоров, Н. А. *Международная торговля и экономическая политика*. Юрайт, 2010.

Kennedy Round (1964-1967): The focus of this round was on tariff reduction and anti-dumping. The Kennedy Round was the first round in which significant steps were taken towards the harmonization of trade rules.³

Tokyo Round (1973-1979): This round was aimed at expanding regulatory areas, including technical barriers and subsidies. As a result of the Tokyo Round, agreements were concluded concerning not only tariffs, but also other trade barriers.

Uruguay Round (1986-1994): The most significant was the Uruguay Round, which ended with the signing of the WTO Charter in 1994. During the Uruguay Round, an agreement was reached on the creation of the World Trade Organization, which replaced the GATT and expanded its functions.

Creation and structure of the WTO

The WTO Charter was signed on April 15, 1994 in Marrakech, Morocco. The WTO officially began its work on January 1, 1995, becoming a full-fledged international organization with its own secretariat and dispute resolution system. ⁶ Unlike the GATT, which was an agreement between countries, the WTO has become an organization with membership and established structures.

The main objectives and functions of the WTO include:

Regulation of trade agreements: The WTO manages a variety of trade agreements related not only to goods, but also to services, intellectual property and public procurement.

Dispute resolution: The WTO provides a mechanism for resolving trade disputes between States, which contributes to compliance with international trade norms and rules.

Monitoring and supervision: The WTO conducts regular reviews of member countries' trade policies to ensure transparency and compliance with trade rules.⁴

Modern challenges and reforms

Since its inception, the WTO has faced various challenges, such as:

Trade wars and protectionism: In recent years, there has been an increase in trade barriers and protectionist measures, which calls into question the effectiveness of the WTO system. An example is the trade conflicts between the United States and China, which have led to increased tariffs and new barriers to trade.

³ Чернышев, С. А. *Международные торговые соглашения и их влияние на мировую экономику*. Экономика, 2008.

⁴ Николаева, О. И. *Мониторинг торговых политик и прозрачность в ВТО*. Международные исследования, 2013.

Dispute resolution and procedures: Some disputes between States have proved difficult to resolve, which has created tension and called into question the work of the WTO dispute resolution system.

Environmental and social issues: The WTO also faces the need to take into account environmental standards and social aspects of trade, which requires updating and adapting rules and agreements.⁵

To overcome these challenges, the WTO is taking steps to reform its structure and mechanisms. One of the initiatives is to modernize the dispute resolution system and update trade agreements to take into account current economic realities and needs.⁶

The history of the World Trade Organization is an important aspect of international economic relations. From its origins in the GATT to the current state, the WTO has played a key role in regulating international trade and ensuring its stability. Despite the emerging challenges and the need for reforms, the WTO remains an important player in the global economy, continuing to develop and strengthen international trade relations.

Rogoff suggests that while the WTO has made significant contributions to global trade, it may need reforms to better address contemporary challenges. He advocates for adapting the organization's rules and mechanisms to ensure they remain effective and equitable in a changing global landscape.

Bagwell argues that the WTO's role should evolve in response to new global economic realities. He believes that while the organization has been successful in many areas, it must continue to adapt to new issues and stakeholder needs to maintain its relevance.

In summary, while many scholars recognize the WTO's contributions to global trade and economic stability, there are also significant criticisms regarding its impact on sovereignty, inequality, and its ability to address broader global challenges. The consensus among scholars is that while the WTO has played a crucial role in shaping international trade, there is a need for ongoing evaluation and potential reform to ensure it meets the evolving needs of the global economy.

Bibliography:

1. Федоров, Н. А. *Международная торговля и экономическая политика*. Юрайт, 2010.

⁵ Яковлева, Н. Н. *Экологические и социальные аспекты в международной торговле*. Экология и право, 2015.

⁶ Тимофеев, А. Н. *Реформирование Всемирной торговой организации: современные тенденции*. Международная торговля, 2020.

2. Максакова, Г. В. ГАТТ и Всемирная торговая организация: история и современность. Наука, 2004.
3. Чернышев, С. А. Международные торговые соглашения и их влияние на мировую экономику. Экономика, 2008.
4. Петров, И. В. Торговые раунды ГАТТ и их результаты. Экономический вестник, 2006.
5. Кузнецов, В. Н. Уругвайский раунд и создание ВТО. Международные отношения, 1999.
6. Баранов, А. В. Создание Всемирной торговой организации: ключевые этапы и последствия. МГУ, 2001.
7. Лобанов, П. П. Функции Всемирной торговой организации. Законодательство и экономика, 2011.
8. Васильева, Т. Ю. Система разрешения споров в ВТО. Право и экономика, 2009.
9. Николаева, О. И. Мониторинг торговых политик и прозрачность в ВТО. Международные исследования, 2013.
10. Григорьев, С. А. Торговые войны и их влияние на ВТО. Экономическая политика, 2018.
11. Соколов, В. Ю. Разрешение торговых споров: проблемы и решения. Вестник международного права, 2016.
12. Яковлева, Н. Н. Экологические и социальные аспекты в международной торговле. Экология и право, 2015.
13. Тимофеев, А. Н. Реформирование Всемирной торговой организации: современные тенденции. Международная торговля, 2020.